

ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-CONSCIOUSNESS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE LESSONS

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Abstract. *One of the global issues in the development of today's society shows the need to pay attention to the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, their constant updating and development. Intelligence among young learners is increasingly becoming a competitive advantage. This requires the need to qualitatively increase the human and intellectual potential of the society, and thereby creates an educational system aimed at ensuring the formation of human capital that meets the current and future requirements of the time we live in, new goals and tasks. In modern conditions, the result of education is not only knowledge, but also their effective use, measured by personal qualities and practical experience, quick adaptation to changes, creative approach to problem solving, formation of ideas and the ability to be a subject of innovative processes for successful operation in a certain field.*

Keywords: *personal qualities and practical experience, quick adaptation, spirit of patriotism, sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws.*

From this point of view, the priority direction of education is the formation of a growing person as a socially active, creative person, a set of tasks that includes the formation of a specialist who is not only competent, but also competitive, quickly adapting to the changing conditions of modern life. This, in turn, requires efforts related to the design of educational research on literary education, the purposeful orientation of students' activities in various communication situations. The task of "educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, as individuals who can resist harmful influences and currents, have firm beliefs and views on life" places a great responsibility on literary education and the content of theoretical concepts in a competitive environment. It serves to increase the intelligence of a person with the ability to acquire information from various sources, increase, pedagogical impact on the educational needs and opportunities of each of them, and thereby ensuring individualization of education. To achieve this goal, the correct implementation of the analysis of artistic works in literature classes will give the expected result. Therefore, it is important to study theoretical approaches and the experience of their implementation, to understand the real world, to successfully adapt to life, to provide intellectual development and individualization of education, which has proven its effectiveness in foreign pedagogy, from the point of view of solving the problem of developing students' cognitive abilities.

It is known that the future of our society depends on the development of a knowledgeable, spiritual person who can understand the world. Literary lessons are important in raising a mature person, in raising them to become a perfect person. Uzbek enlightener writer A. Fitrat, thinking about the position of literature in the fine arts, said, "If the commodity (material) in fine arts is sound, then fine art is music; if there are colors, lines, it will be a picture; stone or other various minerals will be sculpture; if it is stone, wood, brick, earth, it will be architecture; and the movements of body and face (muqam, mimicry) are games (tans); speech, and word becomes literature" and admits that "Literature is to describe the waves in our thoughts and feelings with

the help of words and sentences, and create the same waves in others". Indeed, the role of literature in the development of the student's personality is incomparable.

Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to teach students to think correctly and critically, observe their personal qualities, and form spiritual skills during the lesson. A person's ability to live well in society and make his life meaningful depends on his ability to correctly assess himself and the people around him. These qualities in students begin with learning to correctly evaluate the characters in the work of art. In this sense, literature classes have great didactic potential in developing critical thinking in students. In order to develop the student's competence, the teacher must correctly and clearly define the purpose of the lesson. When setting the goal, he must first clearly define the student's need for learning, the time it will take to achieve the result, as well as the methods that encourage the student to try to achieve this goal. In order to solve it, every teacher should introduce pedagogical technologies into the teaching process based on the student's learning opportunities. In order to carry out this activity, the student is required to concentrate, listen, hear, perceive, understand, store in memory, start recall activities, analyze, draw conclusions, control.

It is necessary to find a solution for everything in order to organize a person-centered education. In a developed person, the solution is different, and in a mentally undeveloped person, there is only one solution. The main principle of person-oriented education is to recognize the individuality of the student and create the necessary and sufficient conditions for his development. A student who can quickly change the situation will have strong growth and development. For this, it is necessary to organize the educational process for individual work, taking into account the psychological characteristics of each student. For special organization, it is desirable for the literature teacher to be able to specially design guidelines for working with educational texts, methodical recommendations for the use of didactic materials, methods of dialogic teaching, forms of monitoring students' knowledge.

It is known that the use of the works of Ch. Aytmatov to form the spirituality of students, to educate them in the spirit of love for the Motherland, will give the expected result. In particular, it will be possible to educate the spiritual and mental world of a person by teaching and analyzing the work "Narrative about Antlered Reindeer".

It was a long time ago. Once upon a time, when there were more trees than grasses on the earth, and there was more life in our country than dry lands, a Kyrgyz tribe lived on the banks of a huge and icy river. This river was called Enasoy.

There is no bigger river than you, Enasoy,

There is no dearer soil than you, Enasoy.

There is no deep pain from you, Enasoy,

There is no one free from you, Enasoy.

... On that day, the Kyrgyz tribe parted from its great elder on the banks of Enasoy. Batir Kulchi was a leader for many years, participated in many campaigns and battles. He survived the battles, but died. The tribesmen spent two days in great grief, and on the third day they gathered to bury the body of the hero. In order to show the four sides of the bright world on the hill where the burial should be done, the grave of the hero was raised above the head: "Here is your river. Here is your sky. Here is your man. You are with us, we are all one clan. Sleep well. We all came to watch you" (from the story on an antlered deer).

It can be seen that the reference in the work, the sacredness of Mother Earth, the river, is created through this work to educate the spiritual world of the student. It is worth saying that in order to absorb each work into the student's heart, it is necessary to organize an educational environment that includes the following for its development and self-expression:

- in the organization and use of educational material of different contents, forms and types, it is necessary to be able to understand that literature is art and that spirituality is the basis to allow the student to choose the methods of completing the assignments;

- use of non-traditional forms of individual and group work in order to creatively activate students;

- creating conditions for independent and mass creative activity;

- organizing work in small groups during training (training, role-playing games, dialogue);

- to find evidence of spirituality in the work, for this it is necessary to develop individual programs and use them.

The teacher should create such an environment that each student, taking into account their characteristics and opportunities for learning, can show their spiritual world and give the expected result.

It should be noted that the literature lesson should be not only informative, but also developing and meaningful. The teacher monitors the behavior and activities of each student and fills the data bank (thinking, interest in science, attention, etc.) Obviously, the image object of literature is a person. As stated by Mario Vargas Llosa, "There are several experiences in world literature to understand a person, to describe his spiritual world in social life. Today's civilization has become humanized and saved thanks to literature, thanks to the thoughts, aspirations and desires that literature has awakened, thanks to the experiences raised in the mind during the journey to the kingdom of fantasy. A sense of self-awareness has gained leadership". Since literature serves for man, for his perfection, it is closely related to spirituality, and it is impossible to imagine it separately. Because spirituality is a concept that expresses the spiritual and mental world of a person. It includes people's philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, and religious ideas. At the root of the term spirituality is the word "meaning". This inner world of man is spirituality. Food gives a person physical strength, spirituality gives him spiritual nourishment and strength. Spirituality is related to enlightenment and culture. Spirituality does not arise in people. It can be achieved only through continuous study, learning, and experience. Therefore, it is true that literature classes are considered a leading factor for spirituality.

"One of the important principles of the analysis of a literary work is the principle of priority of aesthetic principles. Since the work of art is a landscape of the human psyche, it brings readers face to face with the most vivid and touching feelings. In this way, readers get to know other people's psyche. In fact, directing the reader, who has difficulty understanding his own feelings, to feel the feelings of others thins his senses and sharpens his experiences. Only the artistic analysis, where the aesthetic principles are the priority, will open the heart of the reader and save him from insensitivity. Getting rid of carelessness and indifference with the help of a work of art is of great importance in the spiritual development of a person. It is not just a coincidence that the formation of literary knowledge involves the issue of self-awareness, which is the basis of education. Methodist S. Matchonov sees spiritual maturity, which our ancestors have been striving for centuries, side by side with the process of self-realization, and in this regard, he shows the

place of literary education. He notes that self-awareness opens the way to understanding others, thereby understanding the world and its mysteries.

It is known that Chingiz Aitmatov is the writer of the people of Kyrgyzstan, and the writer of all book lovers in the world. His first stories were published in the 1950s. The works "On the Baydamtol Beaches" (1955), "Face-to-face" (1957) have a sharp plot and are full of strong internal mental conflicts. In his stories "Jamila" (1958), "To have and to lose" (1961), "Camel eye", "First teacher" (1962), "Motherland", "Mother Earth" (1963), "Farewell, Gulsari" (1966), the theme of love is sung with great passion. Ch. Aitmatov's works included in the series "Mountain and Desert Tales" were also highly appreciated. In his short story "White Ship" (1970), human beauty, goodness and conflicts of life, ecological problems are deeply explored. In the short story "Olapar running by the sea" (1977), important spiritual issues and the ominous scenes of life during the Soviet era are expressed.

Especially in his novel "The Day of the Century" (1980), universal aspects of our time, strong philosophical, spiritual, moral and social problems were raised. The image of the *mankurt*, who has forgotten his past, is insensitive, indifferent to everything, who knows nothing but obedience and following orders, whose feelings and delicate emotions have disappeared, is one of the main peaks of Aitmatov's work.

In the novel "A Day of the Century", Jolomon, the son of Donanboy from the Naiman clan, a sniper, is captured by the Juanjuans and turned into a mangurt. Naiman's mother, whose child was burned at the spot, searched for a long time and finally found her liver. However, the prodigal son does not recognize her. Let the acquaintance stand still, Manqurt, with his sniper's hands, obeying the orders of his masters, accidentally shoots the bow into his mother's heart...

Love for the Motherland, people, motherland is skillfully expressed in the work. The word "Manqurt" is used figuratively to refer to a person who has forgotten his history, his lineage, his veins. The word "manqurt" has become a popular nickname for journalism, a symbol of a person who has forgotten his values, his origin, and lost his identity. Chingiz Aitmatov's works have become so deeply embedded in people's hearts that even the term "manqurt" (mankurtism) derived from this word has entered into circulation.

It can be seen that spiritual weakness prevails in him, and he is given the image of a spiritual poor person - manqurt, who cannot understand what love for the Motherland, people, and traditions is.

In Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tatarstan, Bashkortostan, the image of those who are indifferent to their national culture is shown. According to the novel, if they say "What do you want?", he says "the moon in the sky". Whoever goes first, frees his arms and legs, takes off the camel's skin from his head and replaces it with a cap, the prisoner who has become a manqurt will remember that person as his master and will become a loyal slave to him like a dog for life. For him, the worst thing in the world is to lose this hat.

The Juanjuans mocked him and threatened that the woman who was crying and flapping around you would come looking for you and take your hat away. Manqurt's eyes light up at this, and his color turns pale with fear. Then his masters give him an arrow and a bow and throw his hat in the sky, and the manqurt accidentally aims at the hat. So, as his memory fades, his abilities and talents remain.

The great writer Chingiz Aitmatov wants the representatives of today's generation, who have lost their identity, but who do everything they can, not to be like idiots. That is why this

generation, which does not know its identity, imprisons and kills its compatriots as "enemies of the people" in the novel. Whoever gives him this authority, this position, is his master. He does only what his masters tell him to do. Tomorrow, late, he will be in pain to please his masters.

Today's events are also the entrance of the victims of the era who lost their memory and identity. These poor people do not even think about whose box they are flying to, who they are raising a hand to, who caused them to be in this situation, they do not even know whose mill they are pouring water into, they do without a word what their masters say who promised them "the moon in the sky", and become drunk with poison killer.

It is known that at the very beginning of school textbooks, ideas are given on spirituality and its place in literary education. For example: works of art have an incomparable importance in the development of a person. A person does not automatically become spiritual and enlightened after being born, does he? A person acquires these qualities only through constant study, learning from teachers, observing life deeply, and gathering instructive experiences. In this process, turning to literature is very effective. ... It is difficult to take away a person who is interested in a literary work. Indeed, there is no science that can compete with literature, especially fiction, in the spiritual development of the student.

The task of a literature teacher is to teach students to understand literature, to be familiar with it, and to analyze each text and draw reasonable conclusions from it. Also, he should be able to inculcate love for books, master the art of expressive reading, learn to draw correct conclusions from each image in the process of studying. In general, any activity in the pedagogically correctly organized literature class has a positive effect on the rise of the student's spirituality, mental, moral, aesthetic, physical and voluntary development of the child's personality.

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